

CLINICAL ASPECTS OF PROSTHESES IN ANTERIOR MAXILLARY DENTAL DEFECTS

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Introduction: The production of facing ceramic mones is a reliable and effective method of conservative treatment to achieve good cosmetic results in the incisor area. This was confirmed by data from a clinical trial involving 20 patients.

Key words: veneer, control, cosmetic result, restoration, integrity, edge retention, permeability of porcelain under edge consideration.

Annotation: With the advent of porcelain in dentistry, its use in metal-ceramic restorations became the most common. Over the years, this technology has proven its effectiveness in restoring not only lateral teeth, but also anterior teeth. Even today, most dentists still use metal-ceramic restorations for prostheses of the anterior part of the dentition. However, the metal frame of such restorations impedes the passage of light. With a thin biotype of the periodontium, the marginal gum in the area of the submerged metal neck of the crown may appear dark . The edge of the thin, opaque porcelain neck directly destroys the path of light through the gum tissue due to the vestibular shelf. In the absence of a metal frame, the passage of light is possible unhindered. Until the 1980s, the main problem in dentistry was the accurate reproduction of the parameters of the prepared tooth. In the last two decades, several variants of the design of metal-ceramic crowns were developed that were used in the manufacture of all-porcelain restorations. The improvement of the physical properties of ceramics, combined with the improvement of techniques for bonding to enamel and dentin, etching and silanization of ceramics, contributed to the emergence of new prosthetic techniques

[7, 8]. The minimal reaction of soft tissues to ceramic veneers is perhaps one of the greatest advantages of these restorations. The possibility of creating a very smooth surface of the veneer makes it possible to maintain a healthy periodontal state and ensure satisfactory oral hygiene . The reaction of periodontal tissues to different types of restorations has been studied in many studies. According to some authors, soft tissues react equally to metal-ceramic restorations and veneers, while others found that ceramic veneers significantly reduce marginal gum inflammation [1, 2, 3, 7]. The increasing aesthetic demands of patients for anterior and lateral tooth restorations have led to the need to develop new materials that provide optimal aesthetic properties with high strength. Currently, ceramic veneers are a real alternative to all-ceramic and metal-ceramic crowns. With the help of veneers, you can quickly change a person's smile without causing significant discomfort and limiting yourself to minimal tooth preparation. Veneers have a natural fluorescence, conduct, absorb and reflect light in the same way as natural enamel. Such a conservative restoration allows to meet the highest demands of patients . 4) [2, 3, 4, 7]. The introduction of the technique of acid etching increased the reliability of veneer fixation. Kaku, Simonsen and Calamia convincingly achieved high adhesive fixation of veneers etched with hydrofluoric acid and treated with silane to composite cements. Such a bond turned out to be stronger than the bond of the same composite cement with etched enamel [8, 9]. With the help of the obtained results, the clinical application of this technique continued to improve and the indications for the use of ceramic veneers gradually expanded. Recently, ceramic veneers have been used for the restoration of incisors after coronal fractures, as well as for the restoration of severely worn teeth. Mid-term clinical studies have confirmed the high effectiveness of such restorations, since ceramic veneers retain good aesthetic results for a long time, meet the highest requirements of the patient and allow to avoid complications from the gum. Most studies report a low probability of veneer failure (0-7%). [2, 3]. However, some studies have shown a high risk of developing

bankruptcy of ceramic veneers , possibly as a result of the presence of predisposing factors such as adverse occlusion or articular movements. 6), significant loss of tooth tissue, use of insufficient fixation means, improper preparation of the tooth and partial adhesion to extensive surfaces of exposed dentin. Nevertheless, porcelain veneers are generally more reliable restorations than straight composite veneers, if the patient is correctly selected and the treatment is carried out carefully. Despite the available data, the question remains regarding the preservation of the effectiveness of veneers in the long term. Can porcelain veneers last as long as crowns, or does the number of failures increase with increasing service life? Only a few clinical studies report the effectiveness of porcelain veneers over a long period of observation. Even less information is available in the course of standardized long-term studies that provide clear data on the clinical effectiveness of such restorations [7, 9].

The purpose of the study was: to assess the effectiveness of ceramic plates 1 and 3 years after intraoral application.

Materials and methods: a clinical study of 20 physically healthy patients with anterior tooth defects was conducted corrected using an all-ceramic constructed prosthesis. In all cases, follow-up assessments were carried out 1 and 2 years after fixation. Clinical effectiveness has been evaluated using the following parameters: aesthetic results, edge repair integrity, retention, marginal permeability, recurrent caries, fractures, vitality, and patient satisfaction. Leaks have been characterized as "clinically unacceptable but likely to be repaired" or "clinically unacceptable but requiring replacement." Porcelain veneer results retain their aesthetic results one and three years after bonding. None of the veneer was lost. The clinically acceptable restoration rate (which does not require dental intervention) decreases significantly on average from 97% in 1 year after bonding to 92% in 3 years. The main reasons for failure were ceramic failure (3% to 6%) and extensive damage to the repair margin area (12%). Defects in the corner areas

of restoration were made particularly often in the contact area between the veneer and the composite restoration. In these areas, significant discoloration was often observed in the restorations (4%) and high caries (4%). In the majority of cases (28%) where one or more clinically unacceptable problems were present, the defect could be resolved without replacing the veneer. Only 2% of cases required replacement in the restoration 3 years after Cementation. Materials and methods in this study, 148 porcelain veneers were placed in 20 patients. Ceramic veneers were fixed in the teeth of the upper and lower jaws (central incisors, lateral incisors, canines, first premolars, and second premolars). The age of patients ranged from 25 to 40 years. All veneers are worn to improve aesthetic results, replace composite restorations or torn and discolored veneers, or correct the color, shape, or position of the front teeth. All ceramic plates have been installed by our company in strict accordance with technical principles. After preliminary preparation, including prophylaxis and replacement of old composite restorations, the tooth was prepared for ceramic veneer. The depth of preparation of the vestibular enamel surface was 0.1-0.7 mm, depending on the position of the teeth and the degree of color change. Note that the natural interproximal contact was preserved during preparation. In the region of the uterus, there is a protrusion at the border of the preparation, usually located at the level of the gingival contour. All ceramic restorations were manufactured in the same dental laboratory using the same ceramic. The inner surface of the veneer was etched with 5% hydrofluoric acid for 60 seconds and then cleaned in an ultrasonic bath in distilled water for 10 minutes. Silanization was performed using Cera Primer (Kerr). On the second visit, the teeth were first separated with a coffee barrage and then ceramic veneers were secured with adhesive. The prepared tooth surfaces were treated and 35% phosphoric acid (3M ESPE) and bond (ZM ESPE) were applied without photopolymerization after each treatment. To secure the veneer, a light therapeutic compound cement (Kerr) was used and applied to the inner surface of the veneer. Then the veneer was

immediately attached to the notch and illuminated with a visilux 2 lamp (ZM ESPE) according to the steps. Fixed protocol. After cementing the porcelain veneers, excess luting silver was removed using a minimally abrasive diamond fresco (Goldstein aesthetic Trimming Diamond Set, Komet) and thorough cleaning. Finally, the uneven ceramic edges of the restoration were polished with diamond polishing paste and a rubber cup. The final treatment of interdental surfaces was carried out using Sof-Lex (ZM ESPE) abrasive strips. Digital clinical photos were taken before treatment, after preparation, and immediately after veneer fixation (main result). All patients returned to the dentist 1 year after receiving their restoration. In addition, 96% of restorations were reevaluated 3 years after bonding. Evaluation methods in both follow-up visits, aesthetic results, fit margin, tooth vitality (VV), fracture rate (FR), and patient satisfaction (PS) were evaluated. Aesthetic results have been clinically evaluated in terms of color matching (SC) in restorations. Marginal adaptation has been assessed by marginal adaptation and retention (KA / R), marginal permeability (MP) and high caries development (SC). Clinical restoration photographs were taken from both follow-up visits. full restoration. Small cracks along the palatal edges were found in 9% of the veneers, such cracks were repaired using composite materials. As a result of large ceramic chips formed 3 years after the operation, 6 veneers (2%) were replaced with crowns. Edge integrity, area optimization and care after 3 years of operation do not violate the restoration. The number of ceramic veneer restorations with well-matched edges along the entire contour is 79%. The number of small defects in the neck and sides during palpation by rodents increases by 14% over time. 148 veneers had large unacceptable defects (8%). The number of repairs with significant transparency (KP2+kpz) significantly increased from 1 (26%) to 3 years (65%) after the control procedure. Unacceptable color changes in the area of the edges of the restoration 3 years after the operation are observed in the area of 28 veneers (2%). Marginal transparency of the neck in the area of the edges of the palatal insulator is often

detected during both controlled visits. Significant damage to the edges of the veneers is detected more often 3 years after the installation of the veneers (6 cases of restorations) compared to a later control visit after 1 year (0 cases of restorations). Most of the significant damage (5 repairs) falls in the transition zone between the veneers, and a complete restoration of the tooth is performed (optional). Only in two cases do serious processes occur on the neck of the veneer in contact with the tooth. About 2.5 years after the veneers were installed, pulp irritation appeared in two teeth. In both cases, type 4 composite sealant was applied to the teeth. Endodontic treatment was performed. Let's take a clinical case as an example. A 30-year-old patient who contacted the clinic complained of insufficient cosmetic care, lack of isolation and shortening. During a comprehensive examination, a diagnosis was made: a general disease of the tooth-friction joint of the II degree. Treatment is carried out taking into account the clinical condition using lateral and frontal frameless restorations. Photography is performed at all stages. A full 13-year warranty for the replacement of worn and discolored synthetic complete dentures and veneers, which improves the aesthetic result, as well as color and size adjustment. ,12, 11, 21, 22, 23, 34, 33, 32, 31, 41, 42, 43, 44. All ceramic veneers are installed by us with strict adherence to the installation principles. The patient was examined one year after the ceramic restoration was installed in the clinic. There was no recovery. After three years, small chips appear on the dental veneer 3.2, which can be polished without compromising esthetics and functionality (Fig. 1). 1). 2). 7). At the moment, the use of veneers is no longer considered an experimental method of tooth restoration. Veneers are recognized as reliable restoratives. Due to the excellent aesthetic properties of veneers and the gentle preparation of the teeth, patients and dentists use them more readily. The reliability of this method of restoration has been confirmed by several medium-term and short-term studies. The manufacture of vestibular ceramic veneers is a reliable and effective method of conservative treatment to achieve good aesthetic results in the

field of rodent treatment. The correct choice of obturation, type of preparation, the presence of composite sealants and adhesives for attaching the veneers to the tooth tissues are components of the long-term clinical success of ceramic veneers.

To conclude: Summarizing the results of this study, it can be concluded that vestibular prostheses with ceramic veneers are a gentle and effective method of long-term prosthesis of the forehead. Three years after the operation, most veneers retain their aesthetic appearance, patients are satisfied, and the number of permanent defects is low. Factors such as occlusion, the presence of various types of sealants and adhesives determine the clinical prognosis of ceramic veneers in the long term. If used correctly, taking into account all the limitations, ceramic veneers represent a particularly reliable type of aesthetic restoration. In most cases, minor difficulties can be successfully eliminated by abandoning alternative restorations. Of course, in order to maintain the healthy structure of the teeth, preference is given to ceramic veneers instead of crowns, if there are no contraindications to their use.

Literature:

1. Ризаев Ж. А., Ахмедов А. А. ОСНОВЫ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОМОЩИ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН НА ОСНОВЕ РАЗВИТИЯ ОБЩЕЙ ВРАЧЕБНОЙ ПРАКТИКИ //ЖУРНАЛ СТОМАТОЛОГИИ И КРАНИОФАЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 3.
2. Ризаев Ж. А., Ахмедов А. А. GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF GENERAL MEDICAL PRACTICE IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN TO IMPROVE DENTAL CARE //ЖУРНАЛ СТОМАТОЛОГИИ И КРАНИОФАЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 3.
3. Astanovich A. D. A. et al. The State of Periodontal Tissues in Athletes Engaged in Cyclic Sports //Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology. – 2021. – С. 235-241.

4. Alimjanovich R. J., Astanovich A. A. СОВЕРШЕНТСТВО ВАНИЕ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОМОЩИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНОГО ПОДХОДА ДЛЯ УЛУЧШЕНИЕ ЕЕ КАЧЕСТВА //JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2023. – Т. 8. – №. 4.

5. Ортикова Н. Глобализация биоэтики в период пандемии COVID-19 //Общество и инновации. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 1/S. – С. 677-682.

6. Ортикова Н. Влияние психоэмоционального напряжения детей на состояние здоровья полости рта //Общество и инновации. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 7/S. – С. 328-333.

7. Ортикова Н. Х., Ризаев Ж. А., Мелибаев Б. А. ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ПОСТРОЕНИЯ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ПРИЕМА ПАЦИЕНТОВ ДЕТСКОГО ВОЗРАСТА //EDITOR COORDINATOR. – 2021. – С. 554.

8. Ортикова Н. Тенденция эффективности профилактических мероприятий путем коррекции психологического стресса у детей на стоматологическом приёме //Общество и инновации. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 181-189.

9. Fakhridin C., Shokhrush S., Nilufar I. ENDOKANAL PIN-KONSTRUKSIYALARNI ISHLATISHDA ASORATLAR VA XATOLAR TAHLILI //JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2022. – Т. 7. – №. 1.

10. Shoxrux S., Shoxrux I., Faxriddin C. PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF ORAL INFECTIONS IN DENTURE WEARERS //International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education. – 2022. – Т. 14. – №. 4.

11. Xusanovich C. F. COMPLETE REMOVABLE PROSTHESIS SUPPORTED BY IMPLANTS //European International Journal of

Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2023. – T. 3. – №. 11. – C. 127-133.

12. Xusanovich C. F. et al. PROSTHETICS A COMPLETE REMOVABLE PROSTHESIS BASED ON IMPLANTS //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2023. – T. 3. – №. 11. – C. 122-126.

13. Sevinch E., Zарафруз B. ETIOLOGICAL TREATMENT FEATURES INFLAMMATORY PERIODONTAL DISEASE //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 03. – C. 241-246.

14. Yusufboy S., Qobilovna B. Z. FEATURES OF THE STRUCTURE OF COPD IN ELDERLY PATIENTS //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 05. – C. 363-368.

15. Yusufboy S., Qobilovna B. Z. STUDY THE EFFECT OF HYGIENIC CARE ON THE MICROBIAL LANDSCAPE OF THE ORAL CAVITY IN PATIENTS USING COMBINED SPLINTING STRUCTURES WITH MODERATE PERIODONTITIS //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 02. – C. 50-55.

16. Sevinch E., Qobilovna B. Z. A STUDY ON THE MORPHOFUNCTIONAL STATE OF ORAL ORGAN TISSUES DURING THE USE OF NON-REMOVABLE ORTHODONTIC STRUCTURES //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 03. – C. 247-253.

17. Shaximardonova E. S., Kobilovna B. Z. RED LICHEN PLANUS OF THE ORAL MUCOSA AND ITS CLINICAL ANALYSIS OF A PATIENT WITH, ASSOCIATED WITH THE EPSTEIN—BARR VIRUS //European

International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 01. – C. 272-279.

18. Yusufboy S., Qobilovna B. Z. STUDY OF CHANGES IN THE ORAL CAVITY IN ENDOCRINE DISEASES //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 05. – C. 357-362.

19. Yusufboy S., Qobilovna B. Z. SMARTBURS II–A REVIEW OF THE ADVANTAGES OF SMART BOR //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 02. – C. 56-60.